

THE IMPORTANCE OF TERMINOLOGY IN THE STUDY OF SPECIALIZED LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In the realm of specialized language, terminology stands as a cornerstone that shapes communication, knowledge dissemination, and understanding within various fields. The precise and consistent use of specialized terms is essential for experts to effectively convey complex concepts, maintain credibility, and facilitate efficient information exchange. This article delves into the pivotal role and significance of terminology in the study of specialized language, highlighting its importance in enhancing communication, collaboration, and learning within specific domains. Understanding the power of terminology is key to unlocking the potential for clarity, consistency, and efficiency in specialized discourse.*

Keywords: *Specialized knowledge, terminology, translators, technical writers, expertise, linguistic knowledge, cognitive linguistic approaches*

In today's society, the naming and structuring of specialized knowledge concepts have become a focal point due to the emphasis on science and technology. Information in scientific and technical texts is conveyed through specialized terms, which act as gateways to complex knowledge structures. Translators and technical writers must have a deep understanding of the language, content, and knowledge level of the audience to effectively convey specialized texts. There is ongoing debate about whether translators need expertise in the specific field to accurately translate scientific or technical texts, with some arguing that only experts should undertake such tasks. While some experts may attempt translation due to their knowledge of terminology, they often find it challenging. Simply knowing terminological correspondences is insufficient, as these units impact the text at multiple levels.

There is ongoing discussion about the level of expertise required for translators and technical writers to effectively handle scientific or technical texts. Some argue that only experts in the field should translate or write such texts, as they believe non-experts cannot acquire the necessary knowledge. While experts with a good grasp of a second language may attempt translation due to their familiarity with terminology, they often find it challenging. Some writers or translators rely solely on their linguistic knowledge to produce scientific or technical texts, but this approach can be difficult. Terminological units have both structural and syntactic aspects, impacting the text at various levels. Linguistic knowledge alone is not sufficient for producing quality specialized texts; writers and translators must also understand the conceptual entities, events, and interrelationships within the text. This highlights the importance of being well-versed in terminology and specialized knowledge representation for successful generation and translation of scientific and technical texts.

Terminology, as a discipline, emerged to address the need for specialized communication and knowledge transfer among individuals from different language communities with similar levels of expertise. The focus has been on developing glossaries, dictionaries, and resources for terminological and translation purposes. According to Cabré (2000a: 37), terminology aims to unify concepts and terms within specific subject fields to enhance professional communication

and knowledge exchange. Terminology has been seeking theoretical principles to explain specialized knowledge representation, category organization, and the behavior of terminological units in various languages. The discussion has led to questions about whether terminology should be considered a branch of Philosophy, Sociology, Cognitive Science, or Linguistics. However, it is argued that terminology is primarily a linguistic and cognitive activity, where terms convey conceptual meaning within specialized texts. Terms undergo linguistic analysis focusing on lexical centrality and usage-based approaches that prioritize meaning and conceptual representation. Historically, terminology and linguistics have had minimal interaction, with terminology emphasizing independence and linguistics overlooking specialized language as a unique area of study.

Terminology encompasses various interpretations and distinctions based on capitalization and context. The field of terminology involves both the study of specialized language, denoted by a capital T, and the units within specific knowledge domains, indicated by a lowercase t. Theoretical approaches to terminology can be categorized as prescriptive or descriptive, with early theories like General Terminology Theory being prescriptive in nature. Subsequent theories have shifted towards a descriptive perspective, incorporating elements from Cognitive Linguistics to analyze the social, communicative, and cognitive aspects of specialized language units more realistically within texts. This shift signifies a cognitive evolution in the field of terminology.

The discipline of terminology originated in the 1930s with Eugen Wüster, known for his work "The Machine Tool," which served as a model for technical dictionaries by standardizing terms in French and English. Wüster's ideas laid the foundation for the General Terminology Theory, emphasizing the standardization and organization of scientific language. However, this theory had limitations in representing the multidimensional nature of specialized knowledge concepts and did not address syntax and pragmatics in specialized language use, hindering its application in translation and text generation. The focus was on separating concepts from their linguistic labels (terms) and emphasizing the distinction between specialized and general language, sometimes suggesting that terms were abstract symbols rather than linguistic entities.

The General Terminology Theory posits that specialized language units can be differentiated from general language words by their singular relationship to the specialized concept they represent and the consistency between form and content in texts discussing this concept. However, this view idealizes specialized communication. Upon closer examination of specialized language texts, it becomes evident that terminological variation is common and influenced by factors such as the expertise and status of speakers, text purpose, content, and audience. It is not uncommon for multiple terms to refer to the same concept, or for a single linguistic form to denote different concepts. Terms also exhibit unique syntactic structures and can function differently in texts based on their conceptual emphasis. This phenomenon is present in all languages and poses challenges for translators and technical writers.

Initially, the primary role of Terminology was believed to be the creation and standardization of names for concepts, with little consideration given to syntax within the realm of Terminology. The General Terminology Theory viewed Terminology as solely synchronous, overlooking the historical evolution of terms. Wüster's key objectives were to eliminate ambiguity in technical languages through terminology standardization for effective communication, promote the benefits of standardized terminology to all users of technical languages, and establish terminology as a practical discipline and scientific field. However, Terminology lacked innovative theoretical advancements due to limited theoretical discourse until recently.

One explanation for the continued adherence to established principles in Terminology is the lack of interest from specialists in other fields such as linguistics, psychology, philosophy, history of science, communication, and discourse studies. For many years, Terminology was viewed as a practical tool to meet specific needs or as a knowledge domain unrelated to language signs.

In the 1990s, new approaches emerged in Terminology, expanding its scope to encompass social, communicative, and linguistic contexts. L’Homme, Heid, and Sager (2003) highlighted Socioterminology (Boulanger 1991; Guespin 1991; Gaudin 1993, 2003), the Communicative Theory of Terminology (Cabr 2000a, 2000b, 2001a, 2001b, 2003; Cabr et al. 1998), and Sociocognitive Terminology (Temmerman 1997, 2000, 2001, 2006) as examples of these new approaches.

Socioterminology and Communicative Terminology Theory emerged in the early 1990s as responses to the global dominance of the General Terminology Theory. These theories offer a more realistic perspective on terminology by examining how terms are used in communication contexts. They analyze terminological units in actual discourse and consider the social and discourse factors influencing different types of texts.

Gaudin's (1993) Socioterminology applies sociolinguistic principles to Terminology theory, explaining terminological variation by identifying term variants in various usage contexts. Variations in terms are influenced by social and ethnic factors, leading experts and specialists to use different terms for the same concept or multiple concepts for the same term.

Pihkala (2001) notes that the socio-terminological approach focuses on the social and situational aspects of specialized language communication, impacting expert communication and term variation. Socio-terminologists argue that standardization is unattainable due to the evolving nature of language. Polysemy and synonymy are inherent in terminology and specialized texts, with term choice reflecting users' knowledge, social status, and power dynamics in communication interactions. Additionally, terminological variation reveals that concept systems and definitions are dynamic rather than static.

Socio-terminology's significance lies in its role as a precursor to other descriptive theories of Terminology that consider social and communicative factors. These theories are grounded in how terms are actually used in specialized discourse, aligning with Gregory and Carroll's (1978: 3-4) characterization of linguistic variation based on use and user. While not seeking independent theoretical status, Socio-terminology paved the way for theories that incorporate social and communicative elements into their principles.

In recent years, linguistic theory has shifted towards a cognitive approach, emphasizing the conceptual network that underlies language. The integration of syntax and semantics has become a focus for linguists, reflecting a similar trend in Terminology studies. Cognitive-based Terminology theories, while sharing similarities with the Communicative Theory of Terminology, also exhibit differences. These theories have emerged primarily in Translation contexts and incorporate principles from Cognitive Linguistics and Psychology to explain category structures and concept descriptions. Notable theories in this area include Sociocognitive Terminology and Frame-based Terminology.

Conclusion

The use of terminology extends beyond specialists, with terminology knowledge being valuable for various professionals, not just terminologists, translators, and linguists. The type of knowledge required depends on one's professional activities and reasons for learning. Institutions

and academic centers play a crucial role in providing diverse materials tailored to different learner groups. Their ability to offer a range of opportunities for terminology learners is based on the multifaceted nature of terminology. It's important to view terminology in three aspects: as a set of needs related to information and communication, as a set of practices in specific applications like vocabularies, and as a field of knowledge that can be studied scientifically in theoretical, descriptive, and applied contexts.

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